

As on 20-01-2020, the following data collection and data entry procedures are recommended for recording crop classification into knowledge base system.

Steps for data collection:

1. The general way is to understand the context of the crops uses in several sources and deduce the classification based on the provided information.
2. The steps might vary according to the creativity of data collectors, capacity and time limitation. In general, the more time spent on the data collection, the more information would be retrieved.

Steps for data entry:

1. Prior to data entry, one should know the following:
 - **'Crop Classification'** is the table to record the classification of a specific crop.
 - Procedures of data entry into the database (how to enter the data into the table); user will be trained for the data entry before entering data.
2. There are 4 fields to be entered, **three** of them are meant to be compulsory for every record.

2.1 Crop ID (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the common name which belongs to a specific crop subspecies, variety, cultivar or landrace.

2.2 Crop Classification (Compulsory)

- This is referring to the classification of a specific crop based on its uses.
- The classification chosen for a specific crop must be suitable and closely related to the uses of the crop.
- One crop may have more than one classification.
- The selection of crop classification is based on 'Classification of Crop' standard by FAO. The available options for selection are:
 - a. Aromatic Crops
 - Crops with aromatic compound and being used for the purpose.
 - b. Beverage Crops
 - A beverage crop is the one that produces a potable beverage other than water. E.g. coffee, tea, cocoa.
 - c. Cereal
 - E.g. wheat, rice, millets.
 - d. Fibre Crops
 - Crops that are grown for the natural fiber that is used in manufacturing industries. E.g. cotton, flax, kenaf, jute, hemp
 - e. Fodder Crops
 - Crops feed to the animal (fresh or processed). E.g. hay, silage, pasture, grain corn.
 - f. Forage Crops (Feed to the animal independently)

- Crops feed to the animal independently. Mainly are grasses and legumes. E.g. alfalfa, foxtail grass.
- g. Fruits
 - E.g. mango, apple, orange
- h. Legumes
 - E.g. beans, chick pea, cowpea
- i. Medicinal Crops
 - Crops with medicinal properties and being used for the purpose.
- j. Nuts
 - E.g. almond, peanut, walnut
- k. Oilseed Crops
 - Oilseed crops are grown for the purpose of extraction of oil, which is contained in their seeds. E.g. groundnut, olive, oil palm, sesame, linseed, rapeseed.
- l. Ornamental/landscape Crops
 - Crops for ornamental purposes.
- m. Pesticidal Crops
 - Crops with specific use as pesticide or other control agents.
- n. Rubber Crops
 - Crops with specific use of supplying rubber. E.g. rubber.
- o. Spice Crops
 - E.g. chilli, ginger, anise, cinnamon, vanilla
- p. Starchy Roots/tubers
 - E.g. potato, cassava, yam
- q. Sugar Crops
 - E.g. sugar beet, sugar cane
- r. Vegetables (Leafy/stem)
 - E.g. asparagus, lettuce, spinach
- s. Vegetables (Fruit)
 - E.g. cucumber, tomato, pumpkin, melons
- t. Vegetables (Root/Bulb/Tuber)
 - E.g. carrot, turnip, garlic, onions
- u. Unspecified/Unknown
 - Crop classification cannot be determined due to lack of evidence.
- v. Other
 - Other class which is not in the list of any of the available Crop Classification.

3. Notes

- This field is to store other information which is related to the crop classification of a specific crop itself.
- It is compulsory to fill in this field if 'Other' or 'Unspecified/Unknown' are chosen at 'Crop Classification' field.

4. Metadata ID (Compulsory)

Draft status

- This field is to link the record to the metadata of crop classification.
- One MUST create a Metadata record in 'Metadata' table before entering Metadata ID.

Reference:

1. World Programme for the Census of Agriculture (2010). Classification of Crops. Retrieved from http://www.fao.org/fileadmin/templates/ess/documents/world_census_of_agriculture/appendix3_r7.pdf